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Roles of Tertiary Education in Effective Management and Curtailing the Spread of Mpox in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper explores the critical role of tertiary institutions in managing and curtailing the spread of Mpox in Nigeria. As a position paper, it relies on secondary data sourced from books, seminar papers, workshop reports, articles, and other relevant literature, which were reviewed and analyzed through content analysis to focus on key themes related to Mpox management. The paper concludes that tertiary institutions have a pivotal role in the effective management and containment of Mpox in Nigeria. Specifically, it identifies several responsibilities of these institutions, including educating students about Mpox, conducting institutional and community sensitization, engaging in research on Mpox, establishing centers dedicated to the study of Mpox, and creating isolation centers. The findings highlight the importance of integrating Mpox education into the academic framework of tertiary institutions, using both traditional and innovative strategies like artificial intelligence to enhance student understanding and reduce the risk of transmission. Additionally, tertiary institutions are called upon to actively participate in community sensitization efforts and to share their research findings with the government and international bodies to support broader public health initiatives. The paper recommends that the government at all levels involve tertiary institutions in Mpox management efforts, with supervisory commissions directing these institutions to embark on extensive sensitization programs. Furthermore, the government should allocate special intervention funds to assist tertiary institutions in implementing Mpox-related programs effectively. Collaboration with vaccine manufacturers and international partners is also recommended to facilitate vaccine distribution across Nigerian states.

Keywords: Effective, Tertiary Education, Mpox, Management

Introduction

The Director-General of the World Health Organization (WHO), Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, has declared the recent surge of Mpox in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) and several other African countries as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) under the International Health Regulations (2005). This declaration follows the recommendation of an Emergency Committee of independent experts, who reviewed data from WHO and affected countries. The committee concluded that the rapid spread of Mpox, particularly the emergence of a new clade in eastern DRC, presents a significant threat, with the potential to spread further across Africa and beyond. In his declaration, Dr. Tedros highlighted the concerning factors, including the emergence of a new sexually transmissible strain of the Mpox virus and its rapid spread in eastern DRC, coupled with ongoing outbreaks in other parts of Africa. He emphasized that this situation is not just an emergency for Africa but for the entire world. Mpox, which originated in Africa and was long neglected, eventually led to a global outbreak in 2022 (Ogoina, 2023). Dr. Tedros stressed the urgent need for decisive action to prevent a repeat of this history.

The spread of Mpox has now reached Nigeria. The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (NCDC) (2024) has been actively monitoring several endemic diseases, including Mpox, which has been declared a PHEIC by both WHO and the Africa Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (Africa CDC). In 2024 alone, approximately 2,863 confirmed cases and 517 deaths have been reported across 13 African countries, a surge attributed to a new strain of the Mpox virus that first emerged in eastern Congo and has since spread to Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda. In Nigeria, there have been 39 confirmed cases and no deaths reported across 19 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) since the beginning of 2024. This alarming situation underscores that Mpox is both a national and international health problem requiring urgent and coordinated attention.

The effective management of Mpox in Nigeria need full involvement of every stakeholders such as donor agencies, Federal Ministry of Health, the State Ministry of Health, states Primary Healthcare Agencies, media organisations, health workers, community leaders and the target audience or beneficiaries and tertiary institutions. The involvement of tertiary institutions is critical because their major functions include teaching, researching and provision of community services that are essential to management of Mpox in Nigeria. Study by Awoyomi, Njoga, Jaja, Oyeleye, Awoyomi, Ibrahim, Saulawa, Galadima, Rowaiye, Olasoju, Idrisa, Olalere, Olasoju, Adisa, Adetunji, Idemudia, Ezenduka, Oguttu (2023) showed that there was disparity in the knowledge and perception of mpox in the study population, and as a result, there is a need to intensify awareness about MPXV infection to enhance positive perception among the respondents. It is based on this that this paper seeks examine the roles of tertiary institutions in effectively management and curtaining the spread of Mpox in Nigeria.

Tertiary education

Tertiary education as a planned and organized educational system designed for the total development of man/woman and the total transformation of society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service. Tertiary education can also be viewed as post-basic and secondary school education that embraces advanced teaching, research and community service (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie 2023). Tertiary education, also known as higher education, refers to educational programs offered by universities, colleges, and other institutions beyond secondary education. It encompasses undergraduate and postgraduate studies, providing students with advanced knowledge, skills, and qualifications in their chosen field of study (Proctoredu, 2023).

Tertiary education is an educational system that advances the implementation of the teaching programme, research programme and community service programme for the socio-economic, socio-cultural

and technological development of a particular country (According to Ogunode & Mcbrown 2022). Ibrahim (2017) stated that higher institutions are very important tools in meeting the socio-cultural and developmental needs of a country.

Tertiary institutions are known globally as provider of solution to problems facing the society. Musa (2016); Ogunode (2020) and Abu (2022) concluded that tertiary institutions and research institutions are the last hope of the humanities when it comes to issues of finding solutions to problems that befall the entire society. Femi (2019) also attested that tertiary institutions are established to provide solutions to society's problems and challenges. Ogunode, Ayeni, and Olorundare, (2024) and Ogunode, Ayeni, and Ogwuche, (2024) noted that the tertiary institutions are established to proffer solutions to national and international problems.

Concept of Mpox

Mpox is a rare viral zoonotic infectious disease (i.e., disease of animals transmitted from animals to humans) that is endemic in several African countries including the tropical rainforests of Central and West Africa. The exact reservoir of the virus is still unknown although rodents, squirrels and monkeys are suspected to play a part in transmission (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention 2024). Monkeypox according to Penn medicine (2024) is an infectious disease caused by the monkeypox virus which results in a rash and flu-like symptoms. Monkeypox is currently spreading globally and within the United States primarily from close contact with an infected person, but historically has also been transmitted to people from contact with an infected animal. Monkeypox is part of the same family of viruses as variola virus, the virus that causes smallpox. It causes similar but milder symptoms than smallpox and is rarely fatal. There are two known types of monkeypox virus endemic in Africa — one that originated in Central Africa and one that originated in West Africa.

Idowu, Ayinde, Michael, Olatunde-Aiyedun, and Ogunode (2021) highlighted that the Mpox virus, like other viruses, can be transmitted from animals to humans as well as from person to person. Animal-to-human transmission may occur through direct contact with the blood, bodily fluids, skin, or mucosal lesions of infected animals, such as monkeys, squirrels, and rodents. This can happen through bites, scratches, handling, or consuming inadequately cooked bushmeat or its byproducts. Human-to-human transmission, according to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2024), occurs when a person comes into contact with the virus from an infected individual or contaminated materials like clothing and bedding. The World Health Organization (2023) further explains that person-to-person transmission of Mpox can occur through direct contact with infectious skin lesions or other lesions, such as those in the mouth or on the genitals. This includes face-to-face interactions (e.g., talking or breathing), skin-to-skin contact (e.g., touching or vaginal/anal sex), mouth-to-mouth contact (e.g., kissing), mouth-to-skin contact (e.g., oral sex or kissing the skin), and exposure to respiratory droplets or short-range aerosols from prolonged close contact. The virus can enter the body through broken skin, mucosal surfaces (e.g., oral, pharyngeal, ocular, genital, anorectal), or the respiratory tract.

Mpox can also spread within households and to sexual partners, with those who have multiple sexual partners being at higher risk. Animal-to-human transmission occurs through contact with infected animals via bites, scratches, or activities such as hunting, skinning, trapping, cooking, handling carcasses, or consuming infected animals (Ayinde, Ohue, Ayinde, Adeloje, Adeleke, Olatunde-Aiyedun & Ogunode, 2021). The extent of viral circulation in animal populations remains uncertain, and further studies are ongoing. Additionally, individuals can contract Mpox from contaminated objects like clothing or linens, through sharp injuries in healthcare settings, or in community environments such as tattoo parlors. Mpox according to Ogunode (2024) is an abbreviation for Monkeypox, which is a rare viral disease transmitted

from animals to humans and from humans to humans and its symptoms include fever, body pain, weakness, sore throat and rashes on the face, palms, soles of the feet, headache, muscle aches, back pain, low energy and swollen glands (lymph nodes) and other parts of the body. The virus that causes mpox is known to spread through *close, interpersonal contact*, including direct touching (including sex), or sharing items like towels and toys. The Mpox virus can spread to anyone through contact with objects, fabrics, and surfaces that have not been disinfected after use by someone with mpox. This includes items like clothing, bedding, towels, fetish gear, or sex toys. Close contact with a pet that is infected, including petting, cuddling, hugging, kissing, licking, and sharing sleeping spaces or food, can spread mpox to a person (Ogunode 2024).

Symptoms of the illness mpox according to Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2024) include fever, headache, body aches, weakness, swollen lymph nodes (glands) and a rash. After about 1 to 3 days of fever, the rash erupts, beginning on the face and then spreading to the body with the face and palms/soles being mostly affected. They can also occur in and around the genitals which is why contact during sex is another mode of transmission. The signs and symptoms of Mpox according to British (2024) last 2 to 4 weeks and may include: Fever; Skin rash; Swollen lymph nodes; Headache; Muscle aches and backaches; Chills and Tiredness. About 1 to 4 days after you begin having a fever, a skin rash starts. The mpox rash often first appears on the face, hands or feet and then spreads to other parts of the body. But in cases linked to the outbreak that started in 2022, the rash often started in the genital area, mouth, or throat. The mpox rash goes through many stages. Flat spots turn into blisters. Then the blisters fill with pus, scab over and fall off over a period of 2 to 4 weeks.

To prevent the spread of Mpox, Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2024) suggested the following measures;

- Avoid contact with animals that could harbour the virus including sick or dead animals in areas where MPX has been confirmed
- Avoid contact with any material that has been in contact with a sick animal.
- Avoid unnecessary physical contact with persons infected with MPX
- Isolate potentially infected animals from other animals
- Practice frequent handwashing with soap and water especially after caring for or visiting sick people
- Ensuring all animal food products are properly cooked before eating
- Use of appropriate protective clothing and gloves while handling sick animals or their infected tissues and during slaughtering procedures
- Report all cases with the associated symptoms mentioned above to the nearest health facility for care, and/or call the NCDC toll-free line on 6232 (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention 2024)
- Healthcare workers (both private & public) are further advised to:
- When caring for patients, always follow standard safety measures, including precautions against droplets, regardless of their diagnosis. These steps are crucial for protecting both patients and healthcare workers.
- Wash hands with soap and water after contact with patients and/or their environment
- Maintain a high index of suspicion for MPX, especially for patients presenting with fever and vesicular/pustular rash in all parts of the country at this time.
- During triage, use precautionary measures such as placing a surgical mask over the nose and mouth of suspected patients and covering any exposed skin lesions with a sheet or gown

- Isolate all patients suspected of having MPX as soon as possible
- Wear personal protective equipment (gloves, gown, and masks) before close contact with suspected cases and dispose of it properly
- Correctly disinfect all contaminated equipment (including bedding) using bleach unless otherwise indicated and dispose of all waste properly
- Report all cases to the State Epidemiologist/LGA Public Health Department immediately or call the NCDC toll-free line at 6232.
- Samples taken from humans for investigation of the mpox virus should be handled by trained staff and sent to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention 2024).

Mpox according to (Ogunode, 2024) has the potential to affect both public and private institutions that includes, including financial institutions, tourism institutions, sports, entertainment industries, health institutions and educational institutions. The likely spread of monkeypox in schools in Nigeria may be possible because the school environment provides a good platform for the virus to thrive. If one case gets into the schools, with the school condition of over-population in most public schools, it is very easy to spread because the monkeypox virus spread by direct contact and the crowded situation within the schools provides a good environment for that wild spread. Monkeypox spreads easily in conditions where susceptible persons are close to infected individuals. Nigerian schools facilities are typified by overcrowding; making them unsafe in situations where there is an infectious disease outbreak such as monkeypox. Mpox can disrupt educational activities in schools if not managed properly.

Mpox can affect teaching and learning in schools. Mpox can affect teachers and students. Mpox can lead to school closure if not well managed by states and countries. Mpox can spread into educational institutions and affect stakeholders in the schools if necessary measures are not put down for effective management. Anyone can get Mpox in the school communities. Mpox can affect school management, school supervision, school programmes like teaching, researching and community services and can also lead to learning loss if not properly managed in a country or state and the schools (Ogunode, 2024).

Roles of Tertiary Education in Effective Management and Curtaining the Spread of Mpox in Nigeria

There are many roles the tertiary institutions in Nigeria can play to ensure effective management of mpor and to curtain the spread in Nigeria. Some of these roles includes; Teach about mpox, institutional sensitization, community sensitization, research on mpox, establishment of mpox and establishment of isolation centre

Teach about Mpox

Teaching is a fundamental responsibility of tertiary institutions, focused on imparting knowledge, skills, and values that enable individuals to contribute positively to socio-economic and technological development (Ogunode & Ukozor, 2024; Ogunode, Somadina, Yahaya, & Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2021). It involves not only transferring academic knowledge but also instilling the right values, character, and behaviors necessary for community development (Ogunode, Ngezack & Usi, 2024). Given the importance of public health, it is crucial for academic staff in Nigeria's tertiary institutions to be actively involved in Mpox management efforts. To achieve this, these institutions should organize training and workshops to equip lecturers with essential information about Mpox, including its transmission, symptoms, and

prevention methods. As curriculum implementers, lecturers engage with students daily and are well-positioned to disseminate accurate information about Mpox. Institutions can mandate that lecturers incorporate sensitization on Mpox into their lectures, dedicating a portion of each session to educate students on the virus either virtually or physically (Olatunde-Aiyedun, Daniels & Olamoyegun, 2024). This approach ensures that students receive comprehensive and accurate knowledge about Mpox, including its transmission routes, symptoms, and prevention strategies. Additionally, tertiary institutions have a responsibility to ensure that all students are well-informed about Mpox. This can be achieved through a variety of educational strategies, including the use of artificial intelligence and other engaging tools that not only enhance students' understanding of the virus but also help reduce the risk of direct contact with infected individuals (Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2024; Olatunde-Aiyedun, Ojelade, & Aregbesola, 2024). By integrating Mpox education into the academic curriculum, these institutions can play a crucial role in managing and preventing the spread of the virus within both the campus and the broader community.

Institutional sensitization

Ogunode, Edinoh, and Olatunde-Aiyedun (2023) emphasized the importance of staff training for effective Mpox sensitization in tertiary institutions. Nigeria plays a critical role in the effective management of Mpox by implementing institution-wide sensitization programs. All tertiary institutions should mandate their medical departments, guidance and counseling units, and information units to undertake extensive sensitization efforts across their campuses. These units and departments should develop comprehensive programs on Mpox management, which should include detailed information on the transmission of Mpox, its signs and symptoms, modes of spread, and strategies for managing the virus. The sensitization efforts should be thorough, ensuring that all faculties, departments, and units within the institutions are adequately covered.

Community sensitization

Tertiary institutions have a significant responsibility to ensure that Mpox is effectively managed within their host communities. Community service is a core mission of these institutions, as emphasized by Ogunode, Aude, and Olatunde-Aiyedun (2022). Community service programs are organized and planned initiatives designed to benefit and improve the well-being of the host communities. These programs are community-focused and are intended to contribute to the development and betterment of the local population. As part of their community service responsibilities, tertiary institutions should actively engage in sensitizing their host communities about Mpox. This includes providing information on the transmission of Mpox, recognizing its signs and symptoms, understanding how the virus spreads, and managing the disease. To effectively reach the community, institutions should use a combination of online and offline methods for delivering these sensitization programs. Public health awareness campaigns are crucial in controlling outbreaks, and the first step in this process is preventing infections. Tertiary institutions can play a vital role in this by raising awareness about the risks of animal-to-human transmission, particularly in areas identified as Mpox hotspots. Key messages should emphasize the importance of avoiding contact with sick or dead animals that could harbor the virus. Through these efforts, tertiary institutions can contribute significantly to the prevention and management of Mpox within their communities (Ekpo & Aiyedun, 2019; Ojelade, Aiyedun, & Aregbesola, 2019).

Research on Mpox

The tertiary institutions should embark on extensive research on Mpox vaccine and alternative solution. Tertiary institutions should direct their researchers, post-graduate students and even undergraduate to carry out research on different areas of Mpox on how it affects the economy, education, health and politics. Ogunode, Jegede, Adah, Audu, and Ajape (2021) observed that tertiary institutions can use their

research programme to address national health problem. Femi (2019) noted researchers which include lecturers and students can engage in research to find solution to socio-economic and health problems facing the society. Ogunode and Olamilokun (2024). Ogunode, Ayeni, and Ogwuche (2024) submitted that tertiary institutions, through their research problems, can provide solutions to global problems.

Establishment of center for the study of mpox

The tertiary institutions can establish center for the study of mpox in their respective institutions. This centers will help to advance information and knowledge on mpox. The centers can organize workshops, symposium and conference on transmission of mpox, signs and symptoms of Mpox, mpox virus spreading medium and management of mpox. Ogunode and Onakoya (2024) noted that tertiary institutions are created to provide solution to the various problems confronting the societies. The main functions of the tertiary institutions apart from the teaching programme, the other two programme of research and community services are problem solving inclined. Tertiary institutions are structured and programme to be able to establish special centre to tackle a particular projects or issue considering as an important and that needs special studies. In the case Nigerian tertiary institutions can establish a centre purposely for the studies of social problem like health issues. Ogunode, Tseveda and Atim (2024) noted that tertiary institutions have the power to create departments, faculties and establish centres to focus on particular studies. Since the tertiary institutions are places to look upon for solution to pressing societal problems. It is expected for tertiary institutions to establish centres that focus on carrying out research on socio-economic and health related problems.

Establishment of isolation centre

Tertiary institutions in Nigeria as part of their roles to effectively manage Mpox and curtail the spread of Mpox in Nigeria can establish isolation centers in their respective institutions. The establishment of the isolation centers can help to prevent the spread Mpox in Nigeria in case there are emergencies or students that contact the Mpox in the campuses. The establishment of isolation centers in tertiary institutions is one of the strategies to employ to manage the Mpox effective in the campuses and ion Nigeria.

Finding

The paper discovered that the tertiary institutions has a crucial roles to play in the effective management and curtaining the spread of Mpox in Nigeria. Teaching about Mpox, institutional sensitization, community sensitization, research on Mpox, establishment of centers on the study of Mpox and establishment of isolation centre are identified as some of the roles of the tertiary institutions in effectively management and curtaining the spread of Mpox in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined the roles of tertiary institutions in effectively management and curtaining the spread of Mpox in Nigeria. The paper concluded that the tertiary institutions has a crucial roles to play in the effective management and curtaining the spread of Mpox in Nigeria. The paper identifies; teaching about Mpox, institutional sensitization, community sensitization, research on Mpox, establishment of centers on the study of Mpox and establishment of isolation centre as some of the roles of the tertiary institutions in effectively management and curtaining the spread of Mpox in Nigeria.

Based on this findings, the paper recommends government at every levels should involve the tertiary institutions on the Mpox management in Nigeria. Tertiary institutions supervisory commissions should direct all tertiary institutions in Nigeria to embark on massive sensitization programme on Mpox management programme. Government should allocate special funds intervention funds to all tertiary institutions to aid effective implement of Mpox programme. Tertiary institutions should share the result of

their researches on Mpox with the government and international institutions. Government should work with vaccine manufacturers on potential vaccine donations, and coordinating with partners to get vaccine across Nigerian states.

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